

ELECTROACOUSTIC MUSIC COMPOSITION IN THE MUSIC SCHOOL OF NICOSIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the introduction of electroacoustic (e/a) music composition to the secondary education through a case study at the Music School of Nicosia, Cyprus. The teaching method focused on e/a music composition, through the processes of guided listening, analysis of compositions, recording, manipulation and editing of sounds, and culminated in a concert with compositions and live sound-diffusion by the students. The objective was to guide students with no previous knowledge of e/a music to compose original works with sounds. It is shown that it is possible, for students of young age, to produce high quality compositions after only 4 months of instruction and tutoring. We find that it is important to maintain a high tutor-to-student ratio and that students with longer teaching periods (2 versus 1 weekly in our case study) produced higher quality compositions. At the end of the project 90% of the students commented that they really enjoyed working on this project and were very satisfied with their results. Especially the students that reached a high level of quality of sound material and manipulation, expressed the desire to continue to listen to, and compose e/a music in the future.

1. INTRODUCTION

The electroacoustic music (e/a music) community, for years now, has been trying to attract a wider audience and a greater number of active participants. International projects focusing on the implementation of e/a music take place around the world with positive and promising results [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Music taste has always been a factor for this, and research has shown that “the tolerance towards unconventional musical styles [...] is assumed to decline with increasing age” [6, 7]. E/a music education seems to be the key to this quest. Having this in mind, researchers and composers of e/a music have been promoting e/a music through workshops in schools. This paper presents a case-study of e/a music composition by students that took place at the Music School of Nicosia, Cyprus. Cyprus is one of the least exposed European countries to e/a music, evident through the non-existence of venues for the support of e/a music performances, and the complete lack of installations or concerts in the island, with few minor exceptions. The goal of this project was to introduce and expose students to e/a music composition through a unique collaboration of an e/a com-

poser and an e/a educator, aiming to light a spark of interest for this music.

2. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

The presented case study took place in the Music School of Nicosia, Cyprus, with 23 students aged between 16 and 17 over the first four months of the academic year 2017-2018. The Music School of Nicosia is the oldest of the 5 public music schools of Cyprus, hosting both lower- and upper-secondary education students. It is a public school with competitive entry, monitored by the Cyprus Ministry of Education and Culture, specially designed around music modules, with leading performers/educators on every subject area offered. None of the students that participated in the case-study had previous knowledge of e/a music, even though they are educated within a specialised music environment. In terms of foundational background, all students had basic knowledge of using music technology and had completed the first level of the music technology compulsory curriculum, which focuses on using the software “Audacity” but not a full professional Digital Audio Workstation (DAW).

The composer and PhD candidate in electroacoustic music composition Dimitris Savva proposed the project as part of an Erasmus+ Working Placement Scheme, under the supervision of Dr Nasia Therapontos, a leading expert in sound-based music pedagogy in Cyprus and currently a music technology teacher at the Music School of Nicosia. The project was implemented within the designated music technology curriculum, with the formal approval of the Minister of Education and Culture of Cyprus.

The project aimed through a specific teaching approach (discussed in Sec. 3.2) to:

- Expand the awareness of the students that any audible recorded sound could be used in the compositional process.
- Motivate them to discover the musicality and the creative potential of sounds.
- Introduce them to the concept of sound transformation and manipulation.
- Guide them to a realisation of the expressive and creative potentials of sound and the specific genre of music has to offer.
- Differentiate the two main different types of sounds that create gesture and texture.

- Expand their awareness on form and structure through the observation of the different ways that sounds are placed in time and space in relation with other sounds.
- Develop an aesthetic appreciation of e/a music.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The project focused on e/a music composition, through the processes of guided listening, analysis of e/a compositions, recording, manipulation and editing of sounds using a DAW. The project culminated in a concert with compositions and live sound-diffusion by the students, using a basic e/a music set-up, an 8 loudspeaker surround sound system.

3.1 Teaching Material and Aims

The design process and delivery of the e/a music lesson-plans, was a collaboration between Dimitris Savva and Dr Nasia Therapontos. The teaching material used was specifically selected by Dimitris Savva and approved by Dr Nasia Therapontos in order to comply with the current music technology curriculum. Both researchers/educators collaborated on the pedagogical processes needed for the implementation of the material. The e/a music compositions used as listening examples were selected and analysed by Dimitris Savva, and guided throughout the project by Dr Nasia Therapontos with implementation of pedagogical approaches (focused listening, body movement, drawing) that could enhance the learning process.

The lesson-plans implemented focused on 2 important aspects of e/a music: i) the sound material, and ii) the compositional process:

i) In e/a music, the sound material used can be literally any sound that may be aurally perceived and captured sonically through sound recording. The compositional sonic palette can be endless from the splashing sound of waves hitting the shore to the rustling sound produced from the leaves of a tree, to the sound of a scream, a laugh, a kiss.

ii) Regarding the compositional process, there is a change in the medium where the composition takes place, changing the process itself. The sound is being recorded, captured and saved in a digital format. It becomes “tangible” in the hands of the composer who can choose to transform and manipulate it into a new shape with new characteristics. This process has been described from many scholars with the analogy of the sculptor that takes a piece of marble and can shape it into a statue [8]. Similarly the composer can choose to transform or not the sounds, edit them and then place them in time and space to form a work of electroacoustic music.

3.2 Teaching Process

The students were divided in groups of 5-8 students each, with lessons taking place in the music technology studio of the school that could host upto 8 students at a time. All

groups had one compulsory teaching period per week, while five students opted to select one additional period per week. All students followed the same pedagogical methodology comprising six steps:

1. Guided listening and analysis of electroacoustic music.
2. Working on a DAW.
3. Discussions on the compositional ideas of the students (Individually or in a group).
4. Guided recording sessions.
5. Composing sessions in the classroom with continual feedback from the tutors.
6. Practical introduction to the spatialisation performance - diffusion on the surround sound system.

3.2.1 E/a Music Guided Listening and Analysis

The first lesson for all groups focused on the listening of music extracts from a variety of composers of e/a music, with different approaches, followed by discussion with the students (Table 1). During these first discussions the researchers aimed to identify and capture the first impressions and thoughts of the students regarding e/a music. These listening sessions followed a guided listening methodology, focusing on specific characteristics of the works, such as sonic material and spatial movement. Through the observation and discussion with the group, the students would analyse the composition and at the end a complete analysis was given to them, written by Dimitris Savva, in order to self-evaluate their findings. The process aimed at expanding the knowledge of the students relating to the various compositional approaches that could be used within the context of e/a music.

Composer	Electroacoustic composition
Gilles Gobeil	Le Vertige Inconnu
John Young	Lamentation Pythagoras Curtains
Trevor Wishart	8 Tongues of Fire Imango
Hildegard Westcamp	Into the Labyritnth
Adam Stansbie	Ctr C Foundry Flux
Sam Salem	The Sun Warms the Memory
Dimitris Savva	Balloon Theories Thalassa Stous Theous

Table 1: Compositions used for teaching material

The importance of the guided listening and analysis of these extracts relies on the fact that these compositions were the student's first ever encounter with e/a music and also their starting point in developing a basic understanding of sound, as a texture and gesture [9]. Moreover, these musical samples would expand their understanding and awareness of the spatiotemporal placement possibilities of sound, as well as relations between sounds. They offered the possibility to observe the coexistence and alternation of different homogenous and/or non-homogenous sounds, as well as the possible ways of creating coherence within a musical work.

The analysis of these extracts helped students experience the types of changes that establish the flow within a musical piece. Changes that happen from transformation and manipulation of sounds and changes that result from any alteration of any of the sonic parameters that define the sound within the composition: spectral content, timbre, loudness localisation and movement in space. Through this observation students came to understand the employment by the composer of sonic changes to create expectation, surprise, tension, climax and resolution. These are in turn seen as the means with which progression and evolution - and therefore structure and form - is been created.

Finally, the experience of the guided listening and analyses influenced the students to develop their own ideas for composition. For example, a guided listening and analysis in the classroom of an extract of 2 minutes from the composition "Balloon Theories" of Dimitris Savva (selected as the composer could present it in person) was followed, after the guided listening, by analysis in the DAW. This allowed the students to identify and listen to every individual sound included the composition.

Before listening, specific tasks were assigned to the students: i) to be able to afterwards discuss how the specific short extract of 2 minutes evolved and progressed; ii) to observe the different sounds that comprised the composition, and the sound parameters and how they change; iii) to discuss the phraseology, loudness and coexistence and alternation of different sounds; iv) to try to describe how tension, expectation and surprise was structurally created within the specific section. In the ensuing discussion, students identified the different sounds they heard and could differentiate texture from gesture. For the example section they could clearly understand the basic structural evolution; the composition was starting quietly and softly and it was becoming gradually tenser and louder creating tension. They could also realise the non expected forceful and loud gesture at the middle of that section and the surprise it caused due to its unexpected presence.

Through the analysis and the detail presentation of the extracts on a DAW, students were asked about the placement of the sounds in low and high spectral regions and to observe the spread to different regions in the

spectrum. They were also asked about space in order to comprehend that some sounds were distant and some sounds were close, and their stereophonic spatial direction. This included the realisation of sound movement in space. Students were then asked to relate these processes with the structure. They were also asked about phraseology; to observe the different length, dynamic envelope, possible change in pitch and movement of homogenous sounds. They could easily recognise these parameters and their evolution and how they form phrases.

3.2.2 Working on a DAW

The students were introduced to the REAPER software, a professional DAW, that was chosen because of its intuitive learning environment. Dimitris Savva prepared a detailed course book on using the DAW and its sound processing plugins. More specifically, students were introduced to various technical aspects of the software, such as:

- importing sounds in the DAW
- editing the sounds
- mixing and alternating the sound
- processing the sounds using time stretch, pitch shift, equalisation and reverb
- automating in time panning, volume and all the processing parameters

The students having cultivated basic music technology skills from previous years could easily follow the step by step course book and complete a variety of small projects using pre-recorded sound material provided by the composer.

3.2.3 Discussions on the Compositional Ideas of the Students (Individually or in a Group)

During several sessions, group and individual discussions with the students took place. These focused on formation of ideas related to their individual composition projects. The group discussions related to form, style and structure, while the individual discussions focused on their ideas and collection of sounds. Through these discussions students had personal guidance from the two educators, for both theoretical and practical issues relating to their projects. Moreover, during group discussions students would give feedback to each other and reflect on their work.

3.2.4 Guided recording sessions

All students were motivated by the educators to record their own sounds to be used in the e/a compositions. Most of the participating students did record their own sounds, including all the students with extra teaching periods, for whom the recording of sounds was compulsory. The importance of the recording sessions resided in the fact

that the students for the first time experienced techniques which allowed them to record sounds from different areas of the school, including outdoors, in contrast with their previous experience with studio recording exclusively. The recording sessions aimed to help them discover and explore the endless possibilities of sounds that can be used in e/a compositions.

3.2.5 Composing sessions in the Classrooms with Continual Feedback from the Tutors

The composing sessions in the classroom were the most important and time consuming sessions of the project. During these sessions, both educators would offer individual help to the students, on technical aspects or issues of working with the DAW or offer guidance and help with their compositions (form, sounds, texture, gesture). The students would continue their work at home.

3.2.6 Practical Introduction to the Spatialisation performance- Diffusion on the Surround Sound-System

At the end of the project, a concert was organised by the two educators and the school, which offered the opportunity to perform the student compositions on a surround sound system, with 8 individual loudspeakers (“Ring of 8”). This was the first time ever in Cyprus that a performance with a surround 8 channel system took place and it offered a great and unique opportunity to the participating students to have a first hand experience with the spatialisation performance of e/a music; sound diffusion.

For the concert, seven student compositions were selected to be performed publicly based on their quality and use of sound material. Students had dedicated time periods to practise different diffusion techniques before the concert and all students had the opportunity to diffuse their compositions. This technique allowed them to achieve movement and localisation of sound within the performance space, through the use of faders, each controlling a different loudspeaker volume output. The students were involved through the whole process of setting up for an e/a music concert, from the positioning of the loudspeakers to the connection of the faders to the driving computer and the loudspeakers.

4. OUTCOMES

By the end of the project, 90% of the participated students had successfully completed their e/a compositions. Around 45% of these compositions included only recorded sounds, 35% included both recorded sounds and sounds from other sources (internet) and the other 10% of the compositions included only sounds downloaded or found from other sources. The 10% of the students that failed to complete their compositions were all from the one period-per-week

sessions, and they lacked entry technological skills, especially working on a DAW.

The students of the two (hour) period-per-week sessions managed to produce higher quality compositions than the students of the 1-hour sessions, with the use of their own recorded sounds and high standard of manipulation and editing techniques at the DAW. All high quality compositions were presented at the concert (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Number of students’ compositions presented in the concert Vs weekly teaching hours

One of the predefined goals was for the two researchers/educators to develop an appreciation for this kind of music to the students. This was achieved as at the end of the project 90% of the students commented that they really enjoyed working on this project and were very satisfied with their results. Especially the students that reached a high level of quality of sound material and manipulation, expressed the desire to continue to listen and compose e/a music in the future.

At the beginning of the project it was noted that some of the students reacted reluctantly to the style of this music, some arguing for its suspense as music, since there was no instrumental melodies in it, and for the use of “noise”. By the end of the project these students produced high standard e/a compositions, commenting on the possibilities offered by the use of sound as compositional material and its creative applications.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The objective of the project was to guide students with no previous knowledge of e/a music to compose an original work with sounds, in the style of e/a music. The fact that these students were all specialised music students allowed the fulfillment of the project’s aim and revealed that it is possible for students of young age, to produce high quality compositions after only 4 months of

instruction and tutoring. It is also important that there were 2 tutors available for a high tutor-to-student ratio at any given time. The students with longer teaching periods produced higher quality compositions.

The researchers aimed to let the students discover the expressive and creative capabilities of the use of sound and realise the importance of the technological medium in the creation of e/a music. This was linked to the development of basic skills in sound recording and in software learning. The 10% of the students that failed to successfully deliver their compositions reported that they did not manage to use the DAW as comfortably as the other students and this cost them time.

Finally, it was important for the students to discover compositional methods and sound processing techniques, that would help them shape their compositions and place their sounds in time and space, establishing structure and form. All these lead to the establishment of musical flow and its related functions of expectation, surprise, climax, tension and resolution, that can produce a high quality composition.

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